

Measurement and Modeling of Radio Propagation from a Primary Tunnel to Cross Junctions

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Abstract—In this paper, we propose a new model for predicting around-corner coupling loss associated with radio signals propagating from a primary tunnel to cross junctions. The proposed model is based on the classic modal method that has been widely used for predicting power distribution in straight tunnels. The uniform theory of diffraction (UTD) is applied to calculate mode coupling coefficients. Simulation results based on the proposed model are compared to measurement results taken in a concrete tunnel and show good agreement.

Index Terms—Tunnel propagation, waveguide, junction coupling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Radio propagation in tunnel environments such as underground mines has gained renewed interest [1-3], partially due to the Mine Improvement and New Emergency Response Act (MINER Act) of 2006, which requires all US underground coal mines to install communications and tracking systems [4]. Most of the published work, however, has focused on the line-of-sight (LOS) propagation scenario where the tunnel is straight and there are no obstructions between the transmitter and the receiver. Another interesting propagation scenario which has received relatively little attention is around-corner coupling, where radio signals couple from a primary tunnel to a cross junction as illustrated in Fig. 1. This around-corner coupling scenario is likely not often seen in road or subway tunnels but is common in underground mines where mine entries are generally crossed by other perpendicular tunnels (called cross-cuts).

Emslie's work in [5] is one of the few prior studies that directly addresses the around-corner coupling mechanism in underground mines. The model proposed by Emslie, however, is a highly simplified model based on radiation heat transfer theory [6], and therefore is only valid for diffuse components of the signal.

In this paper, we extend the modal method that has been successfully used for predicting power distribution in straight tunnels [2, 3] to model around-corner coupling in underground mines. The uniform theory of diffraction (UTD) is used to calculate mode coupling coefficients

Fig. 1. Radio propagation from a primary tunnel (tunnel 1) to a cross junction (tunnel 2).

from a main tunnel to cross-cut tunnels (cross junctions). In addition, around-corner propagation measurements were made at different frequencies and the results are used to validate the developed model.

II. MODELING AROUND-CORNER COUPLING

As shown in [3], the electric field at an arbitrary position within a rectangular tunnel can be viewed as the superposition of the electric fields from an infinite number of hybrid modes ($EH_{p,q}$). The electrical field in the main tunnel (tunnel 1) for a horizontally polarized signal source can be expressed as:

$$E_1(m, n) = \frac{-j2\pi E_{t1}}{a_1 b_1} \sum_{m=1}^{+\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} A_{m,n} \frac{e^{-(\alpha_{m,n} + j\beta_{m,n})z}}{\beta_{m,n}} \quad (1)$$

where

$$A_{m,n} = \sin\left(\frac{m\pi}{2a_1}x + \varphi_m\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{2b_1}y + \varphi_n\right) \sin\left(\frac{m\pi}{2a_1}x_0 + \varphi_m\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{2b_1}y_0 + \varphi_n\right) \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha_{m,n} = \frac{1}{a_1} \left(\frac{m\lambda}{4a_1} \right)^2 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{\bar{\epsilon}_a}{\sqrt{\bar{\epsilon}_a - 1}} \right\} + \frac{1}{b_1} \left(\frac{n\lambda}{4b_1} \right)^2 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\bar{\epsilon}_b - 1}} \right\} \quad (3)$$

$$\beta_{m,n} = \sqrt{k^2 - \left(\frac{m\pi}{2a_1} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{n\pi}{2b_1} \right)^2} \quad (4)$$

$$\varphi_X = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{The subscript X is even} \\ \pi/2 & \text{The subscript X is odd} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

In (1), a_1 and b_1 are the half of the width and height of the tunnel 1, respectively. $\bar{\epsilon}_{a,b}$ are the normalized dielectric constant for the horizontal and vertical tunnel walls. λ is wavelength. E_{t1} is the transmitted electric field which is determined by the transmitted power and the antenna parameters such as antenna gain. Similarly, the electric field in the tunnel 2 can be expressed as:

$$E_2(p, q) = \frac{-j2\pi E_{t2}(p, q)}{a_2 b_2} \sum_{p=1}^{+\infty} \sum_{q=1}^{+\infty} A_{p,q} \frac{e^{-(\alpha_{p,q} + j\beta_{p,q})x}}{\beta_{p,q}} \quad (6)$$

where

$$A_{p,q} = \sin \left(\frac{p\pi}{2a_2} x + \varphi_p \right) \sin \left(\frac{q\pi}{2b_2} z + \varphi_q \right) \quad (7)$$

$$\sin \left(\frac{p\pi}{2a_2} x_0 + \varphi_p \right) \sin \left(\frac{q\pi}{2b_2} z_0 + \varphi_q \right)$$

$$\alpha_{p,q} = \frac{1}{a_2} \left(\frac{p\lambda}{4a_2} \right)^2 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{\bar{\epsilon}_a}{\sqrt{\bar{\epsilon}_a - 1}} \right\} + \frac{1}{b_2} \left(\frac{q\lambda}{4b_2} \right)^2 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\bar{\epsilon}_b - 1}} \right\} \quad (8)$$

$$\beta_{p,q} = \sqrt{k^2 - \left(\frac{p\pi}{2a_2} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{q\pi}{2b_2} \right)^2} \quad (9)$$

In (6), a_2 and b_2 are half of the width and height of tunnel 2, respectively. It is assumed that the walls for the tunnel 2 are made of the same materials as the walls of the tunnel 1 and thus share the same electrical properties. E_{t2} in (6) is the electric field coupled to the tunnel 2 for the mode $\text{EH}_{p,q}$. Note that each mode in both tunnels can be viewed as a mix of four plane waves [1]. Each plane wave in the tunnel 1 impinges on the edge of the corner and the diffracted electrical field from the corner edge becomes the source for the modes in the tunnel 2. As a result, UTD

can be applied to compute E_{t2} and an approximation of the E_{t2} can be given by:

$$E_{t2}(p, q) = \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{-j2\pi E_{t1}}{a_1 b_1} \sum_{m=1}^{+\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} A_{m,n} \left(D_{s,h}^1 \left(\frac{m\lambda}{4a_1}, \frac{p\lambda}{4a_2} \right) \frac{e^{-(\alpha_{m,n} + j\beta_{m,n})z}}{\beta_{m,n}} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + D_{s,h}^2 \left(\pi - \frac{m\lambda}{4a_1}, \frac{3\pi}{2} - \frac{p\lambda}{4a_2} \right) \frac{e^{-(\alpha_{m,n} + j\beta_{m,n})(z+2a_2)}}{\beta_{m,n}} \right) \right] \quad (10)$$

where $D_{s,h}^{1,2}$ are the diffraction coefficients for the two right angle corners illustrated in Fig. 1.

$$D_{s,h}(\theta_s, \theta_d, \beta_0) = \frac{-e^{-j\frac{\pi}{4}}}{3\sqrt{2\pi k} \sin \beta_0} \quad (11)$$

$$\left[\cot \left(\frac{\pi + (\theta_s - \theta_d)}{3} \right) F[kLa^+(\theta_s - \theta_d)] + \cot \left(\frac{\pi - (\theta_s - \theta_d)}{3} \right) F[kLa^-(\theta_s - \theta_d)] \right] \\ \mp \left[\cot \left(\frac{\pi + (\theta_s + \theta_d)}{3} \right) F[kLa^+(\theta_s + \theta_d)] + \cot \left(\frac{\pi - (\theta_s + \theta_d)}{3} \right) F[kLa^-(\theta_s + \theta_d)] \right]$$

where

$$F(X) = 2j\sqrt{X} e^{jX} \int_{\sqrt{X}}^{\infty} e^{-jt^2} dt \quad (12)$$

$$a^\pm(\beta) = 2 \cos^2 \left(\frac{3\pi N^\pm - \beta}{2} \right) \quad (13)$$

The N^\pm are the integers which most nearly satisfy the following equation:

$$2\pi N^\pm - [\theta_s \mp \theta_d] = \pm\pi \quad (14)$$

L is the distance parameter associated with plane wave incidence defined by:

$$L = s \sin^2 \beta_0 \quad (15)$$

where s is the distance from the diffraction point. The subscript ‘‘s,h’’ of the diffraction coefficient in (11) represents the soft and hard boundary conditions, respectively.

IV. AROUND-CORNER COUPLING MEASUREMENT

Around-corner coupling measurements were taken in concrete tunnels located within Grand Coulee Dam in Washington State. The dimensions of the main tunnel were 1.8 m wide by 2.4 m tall with an arched ceiling beginning 1.5 m up the side of the wall. Intersecting the main tunnel was a side tunnel measuring 1.5 m wide by 2.1 m tall with an arched ceiling beginning 1.4 m up the

wall. The concrete walls were very smooth with a single conduit pipe running along the ceiling. The transmitter was placed stationary in the center of the tunnel and was about 70 m away from the junction. The received power was logged as the receiver moved away from the transmitter and then turned into the junction (tunnel 2). More measurement details can be found in [7].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 2 shows a comparison of the simulated and measured received power for four frequencies with horizontal polarization. The corresponding simulation and measurement results are shown in red dashed and blue solid lines, respectively. Since the receiver turns at 70 m, the received power associated with distance beyond 70 m corresponds to the received power in tunnel 2. For each subfigure in Fig 2, the data can be divided into three parts: the first part is the propagation in tunnel 1, the second part is the power transition (where the around-corner coupling occurs) from tunnel 1 to tunnel 2, and the third part is propagation in tunnel 2. The model seems to give accurate prediction for all three parts for 915, 2450, and 5800 MHz. At 455 MHz, while the simulation results for part 1 and part 3 seem to match the measurement results, it looks like that the coupling loss predicted by the model is greater than the measured value. This discrepancy might be because the model is developed based on a high frequency assumption and thus is not accurate at low frequencies. The same electrical property parameters ($\bar{\epsilon} = 8.9$, $\sigma = 0.15$ m/s) have been used for all the tunnel walls.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper we proposed a novel model for predicting radio coupling loss from a straight tunnel to cross junctions. Measurements made in actual concrete tunnels are used to validate the model. The model can be used to help optimize deployment of wireless sensor nodes in underground mines.

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Fig. 2. A comparison of the simulated and measured results for radio propagation from a tunnel to a cross junction.

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